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Multi-Mode Wave Energy Converter (MWEC) for Nearshore Wave Energy Extraction

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Abstract

The ocean is a significant resource of reliable, consistent, and predictable clean energy that is more energy-dense than solar and wind energy. Harvesting only 1/10th of the available wave energy can cover 5.7% of the electricity generation in the United States. However, the high variability of the wave environment creates a challenge against efficient wave energy extraction. This research study presents a Multi-Mode Wave Energy Converter (MWEC) to enable efficient energy harvesting over a broad range of wave properties. MWEC's versatility stems from a re-configurable pendulum system that is attached to a rocking platform, which oscillates through wave-structure interaction. The platform is connected to vertical pistons, allowing different dynamic modes to be excited, including pitching, heaving, and surging. In MWEC, electricity can be generated directly via the axial motion of the piston and via a Scotch-Yoke mechanism that converts the piston's axial motion into rotation. This paper discusses the first study on conceptualization of the MWEC with associated lab manufacturing and wave-MWEC simulations.

Keywords: Wave energy converter; multi-mode; numerical simulation; laboratory testing

1. Introduction

Despite the large number of Wave Energy Converters (WECs) that have been developed on a worldwide scale, electricity generation from marine technologies remains low. Most WECs rely on a single mode to generate energy through wave excitations [1], which can limit their range of application, considering the variability of the wave environment. To address this limitation, a number of researchers have utilized active control technologies or passive approaches to broaden the wave frequency band in which WECs can operate efficiently [2-6]. This research study investigates a new approach that can be used to diversify the natural frequencies of nearshore WECs by a multi-mode WEC (MWEC). The proposed MWEC features multi-mode dynamic capabilities that can enable efficient energy harvesting over a broad range of wave motions. The concept of MWEC is discussed in the following section along with the first experimental and numerical studies used to understand and characterize its performance.

2. Design of the MWEC

Fig. 1-left presents an overview of MWEC. MWEC is based on a double pendulum mechanism consisting of (a) a rocking panel system that is attached to the top of a floating platform and (b) a pendulum mass located below the

platform to provide a re-centering capability. The dimensions of the rocking panel and the pendulum mass are key design variables in MWEC, which can be used to tune its sensitivity to various frequency bands. During a wave excitation, the panel system interacts with the impacting waves to absorb the wave energy into MWEC. This energy is transferred via the floating platform into a set of vertical pistons. Each piston is equipped with a Power Take-Off (PTO) mechanism that uses a Scotch Yoke to convert the axial kinetic energy of the pistons into rotational energy. This conversion is achieved with the use of a gearbox of in-house design, which is keyed to an electric motor and battery storage. To enable energy production at small scales, the gearbox amplifies the rotational performance of the PTO by means of a parallel gear system. The number of pistons can be tuned with respect to the wave environment. Each piston can be reconfigured to incorporate an additional energy absorber similar to those of heaving WECs.

Fig. 1. Overview of a prototype MWEC.

Fig. 1-right presents a schematic representation of MWEC's dynamic modes: heaving, pitching, and surging. The natural frequencies of these three modes can be modified by merely tuning the panel dimensions, pendulum mass, and piston resistance, which facilitates prototype scaling of MWEC. To understand the performance of MWEC under wave excitations a series of computational fluid-structure interaction (FSI) simulations were executed. A part of these simulations is presented in this paper. Furthermore, an experimental investigation of MWEC's piston design was performed in the Structures Laboratory at the University of Houston on a 1:20 scale.

3. Dynamic modeling of the MWEC

The dynamics of MWEC were studied by decoupling it into two subsystems: the gearbox of the PTO mechanism and the MWEC assembly without the PTO mechanism. The PTO mechanism consists of a Scotch Yoke, a gearbox, and a generator. A preliminary quality check was performed on the experimental assembly of the PTO mechanism to optimize the planetary gearset by minimizing frictional losses and ensuring adequate torque capacity. The MWEC assembly without the PTO mechanism was examined using computational FSI simulations, which intended to tune its hydrodynamic performance under various sea states. The FSI simulations were performed using the Coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian (CEL) method of ABAQUS/Explicit.

3.1. Experimental investigation of the PTO mechanism

The first prototype design of the PTO mechanism was manufactured on a 1:20 scale and tested under uniaxial cyclic loading. The preliminary experimental protocol along with the gearbox design are presented in Fig. 2. The manufacturing process included the 3D printing of in-house CAD models of a single-acting piston and the gearbox, while a commercial DC motor was implemented to extract the voltage output during testing. Due to the lack of technical specifications for the DC motor, a calibration factor was derived by connecting the shaft of two identical motors and using a DC Power Supply along with a multimeter to correlate the electrical current input with the voltage

output. During operation of the PTO mechanism, the linear motion induced by the test frame to the piston was converted to rotary motion by the crank pin protruding from the yoke disc. The input angular velocity was amplified by four parallel planetary gearsets each designed [8] for an amplification factor of $n_{amp}^{Gearset} = 4$, which results to a total of $n_{amp}^{Gearbox} = 256$ using Willi's formula:

$$(R - 1) \cdot \omega_c = R \cdot \omega_r - \omega_s \quad (1)$$

$$R = -N_r/N_s$$

where the subscript s refers to the sun gear; r refers to the locked ring gear; c refers to the carrier that connects the planet gears; ω is the angular velocity; R is the gear train ratio; and N is the number of teeth in each gear. The results indicated that the PTO was able to withstand the torque demand. However, some modifications were made to improve its performance. These modifications included: re-evaluation of the epicyclic gearset to limit the torque on the carrier and therefore the shear stresses at the crank pin; redesign of the gears' pitch to reduce backlash and limit spurious vibrations of the unsupported sun gear; and use of different materials and lubricants to minimize friction losses.

Fig. 2. Graphical representation of the experimental investigation of the PTO mechanism.

3.2. Numerical fluid-structure interaction of the MWEC

The hydrodynamic response of MWEC was numerically investigated. The analysis domain along with the model of the decoupled subsystems are shown in Fig. 3. The following assumptions were made in the finite element model:

- Due to MWEC's axial symmetry, only half of the system was included in the numerical wave tank.
- The panel and platforms of the MWEC were modeled as rigid bodies.
- The single-acting pistons were implemented as translational springs.
- Energy loss due to friction in the gearbox and absorbed energy by the PTO were accounted for with linear dashpots.
- Buoyant action of the floater and the panel-platform system was simulated by an equivalent nodal force with a direction opposite to gravity.
- The weight of the MWEC and that of the concentrated mass were simulated as nodal masses with rotary inertia.

The amount of energy converted to electricity through the PTO is proportional to the amplitude of the motion of the oscillating system [9]. Thus, to maximize power capture, a large Dynamic Amplification Factor (DAF) corresponding to the heaving and pitching natural frequencies is desired. To maximize DAF , an eigenfrequency analysis is required for the MWEC to possess natural frequencies (f_{wec}) close to those of the incident waves (f_{wave}) for each distinct sea state. By tuning the mass, rotary inertia, and stiffness properties of the MWEC model, it is possible to modify the eigenfrequencies of pitching and heaving to capture the desired range of f_{wec} . An example of defining DAF is shown in equation (2), where ξ represents the critical damping ratio of the dynamic system.

$$DAF = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{f_{wave}}{f_{wec}}\right)^2 + \left(2 \cdot \xi \cdot \frac{f_{wave}}{f_{wec}}\right)^2}} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 3. Computational fluid-structure interaction (FSI) of the MWEC.

Design of MWEC is based on a parameterization of the following ratios:

- $m_{WEC} / \sum_{i=1}^n K_i$, which is the mass of the MWEC over the total stiffness provided by the system of parallel single-acting pistons.
- $m_{WEC} \cdot g / F_{buoy} = 1$, which is the ratio of the self-centering forces of gravity and buoyancy at a calm sea state.
- $(K_{piston} \cdot d_{SWL}) / F_{hydro} \cdot u_{piston}^{max} \geq 0.40/m$, which is the numerically derived relation for system stability, and it relates: the immersed surface length of MWEC, d_{SWL} , the maximum stroke of a single-acting piston, u_{piston}^{max} , the stiffness coefficient of a single-acting piston, K_{piston} , and the hydrodynamic force, F_{hydro} ; where the limit of 0.40/m was empirically determined based on the present numerical study.

In addition, the PTO damping in the numerical simulation was considered as the result of two additive damping properties: (a) the generator damping which accounts for the converted energy in each oscillation cycle (c_{gen}), adopted from a previous study [10], and (b) the mechanical damping (c_m) due to frictional dissipation introduced by the gearbox's operation, which was estimated per [11].

3.3. Numerical Results

The numerical performance of MWEC was evaluated for wave conditions common to the coastal region of San Diego, CA. Hindcast wave data were obtained from the USACE marine station ST84160 [12]. The FSI simulation lasted for one minute and the wave height time series reflected monochromatic wave conditions pertaining to the station's location. Finally, a finite element contact analysis of a solitary gearset was performed in ABAQUS/Explicit to obtain the frictionally dissipated energy in one operational cycle, in order to calculate the mechanical damping coefficient. The properties of the numerical model are summarized in Table 1.

The results of the FSI simulation are presented in Fig. 4. The oscillation amplitude of the single-acting piston was considerable in the simulation where the PTO damping was excluded ($c_{PTO} = 0$), with the stroke length of the piston reaching displacements up to 1.5 m which exceeded the desired capacity of the system design. In contrast, when the PTO viscous damping was included ($c_{PTO} = 10^5 \text{ N} \cdot \text{s/m}$), the system operated within reasonable stroke limits. Finally, the percent participation of each mode (i.e., heaving, surging, and pitching) in the piston's axial deformation was calculated, with the heaving mode, T_{heave} , dominating due to its proximity to the wave period T_m . However, it is shown that all three modes contributed asynchronously to the piston's motion, indicating a potential to harvest energy via all three modes. In future work, further optimization of the gearbox and the system's overall stiffness will be studied to improve MWEC's overall performance.

Table 1. Parameters and properties of numerical simulations.

Wave condition parameters	Station Name: ST84160
Significant wave height, H_s	1.0 m
Mean period, T_m	8.0 seconds
Numerical simulation duration	60 seconds
Finite Element Model: MWEC FSI	Station Name: ST84160
Wall height, H_w	4 m
Nodal mass, m_{WEC}	120 kg
Nodal mass rotary inertia, I_{ii}	120 kg · m ²
Single-acting piston's stiffness, K_{piston}	500 N/m
Buoyant nodal force, F_{buoy}	1177.2 N
Heaving period, T_{heave}	8 seconds
Surging period, T_{surge}	≅ 0 seconds
Pitching period, T_{pitch}	4 seconds
Mass over stiffness ratio, $m_{WEC} / \sum_{i=1}^2 K_i$	0.12 kg · m/N
Finite Element Model: Solitary Gearset	
Mechanical friction coefficient, μ	0.05 (—)
PTO damping coefficient, c_{pto}	10 ⁵ N · s/m

Fig. 4. Results of the numerical FSI study on the performance of the MWEC in regular waves.

4. Conclusions

This paper presented a new WEC system, named MWEC, to generate energy by combining heaving, pitching, and surging responses. This capability of MWEC stems from the combination of axial and rotational kinematics that are enabled by multiple pistons, which allow different dynamic modes to be excited. The MWEC was studied by means of high-fidelity computational fluid-structure interaction [13] simulations and a proof-of-concept for its piston design was performed experimentally at a 1:20 scale. Future work intends to optimize MWEC's design by considering wave frequency bands pertaining to various nearshore environments in the United States, while a 1:20-scale flume testing of MWEC will provide the first comprehensive experimental evidence to better understand its performance.

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